

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, SPECTRAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUND 3*

R	R'	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	$\lambda_{\max}$ cm^{-1}	% oedema inhibition*	% protection against writhing*
H	N-Morpholine	35.2	110–111	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$	318	56.32	45.55
H	N-Piperidine	37.7	135–136	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$	320	68.28	48.79
H	N,N-Dibutyl	33.6	237–239	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$	308	64.36	42.37
H	N,N-Dicyclohexyl	30.3	203–205	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{37}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$	311	62.48	40.53
OC_2H_5	N-Morpholine	39.3	98–100	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$	317	70.32	57.02
OC_2H_5	N-Piperidine	40.1	118–119	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$	319	76.41	66.66
OC_2H_5	N,N-Dibutyl	37.7	213–215	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$	310	68.56	60.33
OC_2H_5	N,N-Dicyclohexyl	36.5	198–201	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{39}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$	322	64.20	53.70
CH_3	N-Morpholine	34.9	119–121	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$	321	65.81	52.38
CH_3	N-Piperidine	35.8	126–128	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$	319	69.23	63.80
CH_3	N,N-Dibutyl	32.6	193–195	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$	314	60.12	57.66
CH_3	N,N-Dicyclohexyl	31.0	177–179	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{37}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$	316	58.84	50.27
Indomethacin						90.32	—
Aspirin						—	87.28

*Coefficient of variation was within 1.5 to 3.6%.

analgesic activity was measured in terms of percentage protection,

$$\% \text{ Protection} = 100 - (D/C \times 100)$$

where, D is average writhing response for compound tested and C the average writhing response for control (Table 1).

Antiinflammatory activity: The activity was measured by carragenan induced rat paw oedema method⁶ using digital plethysmometer. Young albino rats weighing 100–200 g of either sex were used. A group of five animals was taken for testing at one dose level. One group was employed as control, while to two groups indomethacin (10 mg/kg) was given as standard drug. A 10% Tween-80 for control and suspension of test compounds at 30 and 10 mg/kg in 10% Tween-80 were injected intraperitoneally. After 20 min, carragenan (200 mcg/rat) was injected into planter tissue of right hind paw of rats of each group and the increase in paw volume was recorded. After 3 h inhibition of inflammation, if any, was measured by recording rat paw volume. Antiinflammatory activity was measured in terms of % inhibition of oedema,

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{V_0 - V_t}{V_0} \times 100$$

where, V_0 and V_t are average increase in paw volume of control and test animal, respectively. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds tested for analgesic and antiinflammatory activities showed promising results. 5-Ethoxy-1,3-dipiperidinomethylethyl-2-benzimidazole thioacetate showed potent analgesic and antiinflammatory activities. Amongst the others, compounds having 5-ethoxy as substituent showed good analgesic activity. Mannich bases with morpholine and piperidine as substituents seemed to favour analgesic-antiinflammatory activities.

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References

1. S. BAHADUR, A. K. GEOL and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1163; V. M. REDDY, M. A. B. CHARY and S. M. REDDY, *Indian Drugs Pharm. Ind.*, 1980, **15**, 7; R. S. VARMA, V. A. SINGH, H. N. VERMA and S. D. DWIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 73; A. HUNGER, J. KEBORLET and K. HOVMANN, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1960, **43**, 1032; T. GORO, Y. KOICHIRO and K. TOSHIKO, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1980, **23**, 734.
2. R. S. VARMA and D. CHATTERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 1077; G. HASEGAWA and A. KOTANI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, **83**, 206268.
3. J. A. VANALLAN and B. D. DEACON, *Org. Synth.*, 1950, **30**, 56.
4. L. B. WITKIN, C. F. HUEBNER, F. GALD, E. O'KEEFE, P. SPITALETTA and A. J. PLUMMER, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1961, **133**, 400.
5. C. A. WINTER, E. A. RISLLEY and G. W. NUSS, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1962, **111**, 544.

Synthesis of some New Isonicotinoylazopyrazoles

RAJEEV JAIN*, PRATIBHA PANDEY and NAMRATA JAIN
School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University,
Gwalior-474 011

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SULPHA drugs are well known for their various physiological activity¹⁻³. Isoniazid is an established antitubercular drug. In the light of the importance of sulpham drugs, isoniazid and considering the biological activity exhibited by azo group, it was considered worthwhile to combine the sulpham drugs with isoniazid through azo group in order to

enhance the overall activity of the resulting molecule.

N-Isonicotinoyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-(4'-sulphamoylphenyl)azopyrazoles have been synthesised by diazotising sulphanilamides and coupling the diazotised product with the compounds containing active methylene group, viz. pentane-2,4-dione and 4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-dione, followed by the condensation with isonicotinoylhydrazine.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (DMSO-d_6) on a Perkin-Elmer R-35 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard, and mass spectra on a JEOLMS-DX 300 instrument. All the melting points are uncorrected.

Extraction of sulpha drugs: Drugs which were commercially available in pure form, viz. sulphadiazine, sulphanilamide, sulphaguanidine were taken as such, whereas the others were extracted from the various combinations of drugs available in the market. The drugs were extracted from commercially available sulpha drugs by the following method. The drug sample (0.5 g) was powdered and triturated with chloroform (2×5.0 ml). The residue was triturated with dilute ammonia solution (10 ml) for 5 min followed by addition of water (10 ml). The filtrate was then warmed to expel most of the ammonia. The resulting mass on cooling and acidification with acetic acid yielded a solid which was dried at 100° .

3-(4'-Sulphamoylphenyl)hydrazonopentane-2,4-diones (1): Sulphanilamide (0.01 mol, 1.72 g) was

dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (4 ml) and water (5 ml) and cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. Cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.01 mol, 0.69 g) was then added to it. The diazonium salt so obtained was filtered in already cooled ethanolic solution of sodium acetate (10.0 g) and pentane-2,4-dione (0.01 mol). The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals (1; 80%), m.p. 90° (Found: N, 14.50. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{N}_3\text{S}$ calcd for: N, 14.80%); M^+ 283; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 240 (NH_2), 3 100 (NH), 1 140 (SO_2), 1 630 (C=N), 1 670 (C=O) and 740 cm^{-1} (Ph); δ (DMSO-d_6) 2.76, 2.82 (6H, $2 \times \text{COCH}_3$), 7.85 (H, NH), 14.50 (NH-N=C-hydrogen bonded) and 8.3 (Ar).

Another series of the hydrazones (2) were synthesised by taking 4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-dione instead of pentane-2,4-dione. The physical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

***N*-Isonicotinoyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-(4'-sulphamoylphenyl)azopyrazole (3):** To 4-(4'-sulphamoylphenyl)hydrazonopentane-2,4-dione (0.002 mol, 0.566 g) dissolved in acetic acid (10.0–15.0 ml), a solution of isonicotinoylhydrazine (isoniazid) (0.002 mol, 0.274 g) in acetic acid was added and the mixture refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was allowed

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1–3*

R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Colour	Mol. formula
3-(4'-Sulphamoylphenyl)hydrazono-pentane-2,4-diones (1)				
H	185	80	Yellow	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{N}_3\text{S}$
Guanido	200	60	Yellow	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$
2,6-Dimethyl-pyrimidinyl	180	70	Dark yellow	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$
2,4-Dimethyl-pyrimidinyl	190	85	Yellow	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Pyrimidinyl	170	70	Light yellow	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Acetyl	180	55	Bright yellow	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Phenylazoyl	205	80	Brown	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Methiazoyl	225	83	Dark yellow	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Thiazoyl	155	70	Dark yellow	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Methoxy-pyrazinoyl	190	60	Bright yellow	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Methoxazoyl	175	75	Yellow	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$
3-(4'-Sulphamoylphenyl)hydrazono-4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-diones (2)				
H	210	60	Dark yellow	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Guanido	240	65	Yellow	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{S}$
2,6-Dimethyl-pyrimidinyl	190	60	Reddish yellow	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{S}$
2,4-Dimethyl-pyrimidinyl	230	50	Light yellow	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Pyrimidinyl	190	75	Yellow	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Acetyl	230	70	Yellow	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Phenylazoyl	177	75	Greenish yellow	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Methiazoyl	212	65	Yellow	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Thiazoyl	170	80	Yellow	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Methoxy-pyrazinoyl	145	60	Bright yellow	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{S}$
Methoxazoyl	190	65	Yellow	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{S}$

(Table 1 contd.)

N-Isonicotinoyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-(4'-sulphamoylphenyl)azopyrazoles (3)				
H	240	40	Light brown	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃ S
Guanido	245	60	Yellow oohor	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₃ S
2,6-Dimethylpyrimidinyl	250	55	Dirty green	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₃ S
2,4-Dimethylpyrimidinyl	240	56	Dirty brown	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₃ S
Pyrimidinyl	215	60	Dirty brown	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₃ S
Acetyl	260d	55	Dirty brown	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃ S
Phenylazoyl	240	50	Dust colour	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₃ S
Methiazoyl	230d	55		C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₃ S
Thiazoyl	160	50	Yellow colour	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃ S
Methoxy-pyrazinoyl	225	65	Greyish black	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₃ S
Methoxazoyl	250	60	Light brown	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃ S

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

to cool overnight. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as light brown crystals (3; 60%), m.p. 215° (Found: N, 24.00. C₂₁H₁₈N₆O₃S calcd. for: N, 24.19%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 150 (NH), 1 150-1 320 (SO₂), 1 530-1 580 (N=N), 1 660 (CO), 2 950-2 960 (CH₃) and 760 cm⁻¹ (Ph); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.50 (6H, 2CH₃), 7.85 (H, NH) and 8.0-8.40 (Ar).

The other derivatives (3) were prepared in the same way by varying the substituent (Table 1), viz., R=guanido; 2,4-dimethylpyrimidinyl; 2,6-dimethylpyrimidinyl; acetyl; pyrimidinyl; phenazoyl; methiazoyl; thiazoyl; methoxy pyrazinoyl; and methoxazoyl; and their characteristics are given in Table 1.

N-Isonicotinoyl-3-methyl-6-aminophenyl-4-(4'-sulphamoylphenyl)azopyrazole (3a): To a solution of 2-(4'-sulphamoylphenyl)hydrazono-1-aminobutane-1,3-dione (2; 0.002 mol) in acetic acid (20.0 ml), a solution of isonicotinoylhydrazine (0.002 mol) in acetic acid was added and the mixture refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then kept overnight and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol as brown crystals (3a; 55%), m.p. 235° (Found: N, 23.42. C₂₄H₁₉N₇O₃S calcd. for: N, 20.20%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 145 (NH), 1 160-1 320 (SO₂), 1 530-1 570 (N=N), 1 665 (CO), 2 950-2 960 (CH₃) and 760 cm⁻¹ (Ph).

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References

1. M. GUARNERI, *Boll. Chim. Farm.*, 1960, 99, 269.
2. C. ALBERTI and G. BRIGONZIO, *Farmaco (Pavia) Ed. Sci.*, 1961, 16, 557.
3. E. I. PADRISKAYA, I. I. GRANDBERG, G. N. PERSHIN, A. N. KOST, L. G. OVSENEVA and W. P. TINGH, *Vestn. Mosk. Univ., Khim.*, 1963, 1, 69.
4. C. N. FOX, *Science*, 1952, 116, 129.

Synthesis of s-Triazine Derivatives

K. R. DESAI* and M. M. PATHAK

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007

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S-Triazines^{1,2} and urea and thiourea derivatives^{3,4} possess wide range of biological activity. With a view to study their antibacterial activity, N¹-(2,4-dianilino-s-triazine-6-yl-aminoacetyl)-N²-arylureas (2) and N¹-(2-aryl-amino-4- α,β -dicarboxyethylamino-s-triazine-6-yl)-N²-o-nitrophenylthioureas (4) were synthesised. Reaction of N-(2,4-dianiline-s-triazine-6-yl)-aminoacetyl chloride (1) with N-arylureas gave 2, and 4 were obtained by the reaction of 3 with o-nitrophenylthiourea. The antibacterial activity of 2 and 4 has been studied by cup-plate method at a concentration of 3 mg ml⁻¹.

